

Highlights

A hybrid MRAC-PI approach to regulate pH in raceway reactors for microalgae production

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- Hybrid MRAC-PI control scheme enhances pH regulation in raceway reactors for microalgae production.
- The proposed scheme adapts effectively to dynamic variations in the controlled variable, caused by changes in environmental conditions.
- Thorough simulation testing and comparison with the classical PI controller is presented.
- Practical validation in the real reactor is carried out.

A hybrid MRAC-PI approach to regulate pH in raceway reactors for microalgae production

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Abstract

This study presents the design, analysis and experimental evaluation of a hybrid Model Reference Adaptive Control (MRAC) structure for pH regulation through CO₂ injection in an open raceway reactor, addressing the nonlinear and time-varying dynamics of outdoor microalgae production systems. Conducted at the IFAPA center-University of Almería, the research compares the MRAC's performance with traditional control solutions in these processes. Results indicate that the hybrid MRAC controller significantly outperforms conventional controllers, as demonstrated by performance indices. The MRAC's ability to adapt to varying conditions was particularly noteworthy, enabling real-time adjustments and effective pH regulation. During continuous operation in real facilities for twelve days in two different months, the MRAC maintained the pH within the desired range, highlighting its robustness and suitability for industrial applications in microalgae photobioreactors. These findings contribute to the development of efficient and adaptive solutions for complex industrial processes, promoting sustainable and cost-effective microalgae production.

Keywords: Adaptive control, MRAC, Microalgae production, pH regulation

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1. Introduction

It is well known that the growth of population, the extensive use of fossil fuels and the intensive urbanization experienced in the last decades have come with serious environmental problems. Society is currently facing hard consequences regarding water contamination and shortage, global warming and climate changes. In this context, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was launched in 2015 to reduce poverty and set the world on a path of peace, prosperity and opportunity for all on a healthy planet [1]. Among its 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), issues such as the need for greater use of clean and sustainable energy, the fight against climate change or the lack of fresh water are addressed.

In this context, microalgae production emerges as a promising solution. They present several positive aspects such as: (i) they do not impact on human or animal food chains, (ii) they are very rich in oil content, being a suitable biomass for biofuel, (iii) they are produced in an aqueous medium, which may be waste water, (iv) they generate O_2 , and (v) they diminish CO_2 by up taking it for photosynthesis [2]. In addition, they present a major biomass yield and photosynthetic rate compared to other plants and can be grown throughout the year in areas unsuitable for agriculture [3].

In this way, microalgae are not only suitable for producing a variety of products (biofuel, biofertilizer, or even nutritional supplements) but also a great solution for greenhouse gas mitigation and removal of pollutants from wastewater [3].

Microalgae can be produced by different methods and under several conditions. One of the most important factors is the type of reactor used, which should be designed according to the strain produced, the purpose of it, and the weather conditions of the production location [4]. The main classification of those is divided into closed and open reactors. Open reactors are large shallow ponds to allow a better penetration of sunlight and therefore a higher productivity. The most widely used worldwide are the raceway reactors, covering more than 90% of the total production. These generally require a low initial investment, are easily scalable and have low energy consumption, but are exposed to environmental contamination and most of the operation conditions cannot be controlled. On the other hand, closed reactors present a physical separation between the culture and the environment, avoiding external contamination. This type of reactors allow a higher production level and a better quality biomass, but have much more expensive production costs,

high levels of energy consumption and are difficult to scale up [5]. This work is focused on open reactors, as they are the most extensively used in industry and more difficult to control.

To make this technology sustainable, feasible, and economically viable, it is necessary to develop successful production technologies for targeted production of biomass [6]. Microalgae growth depends on several factors among which are light, temperature, nutrient concentration, pH and dissolved oxygen. Operational factors such as dilution rate, depth and harvest frequency are also influential dealing with microorganisms growth [7].

Temperature is one of the most important environmental factors that influences microalgae growth rate, cell size, biochemical composition and nutrient requirements [8]. However, this could only be controlled by using solutions based on heat exchangers or external boilers, increasing considerably the operation costs [9]. Light is also an important factor, as it is the energy source during the photoautotrophic growth phase and organisms use it to convert carbon dioxide to organic compounds. The growth rate is maximal at saturation intensity and decreases with both increase or decrease in light intensity as a function of the strain and culture temperature [8]. Another variable that should be taken care of is dissolved oxygen, given that is necessary for respiration, but a high amount of it can threaten the survival of the microalgae and lead to inhibition of photosynthetic activity [10]. Concentrations over 13.5 mg/L decrease the growth rate by 25 % and concentrations above 22.5 mg/L reduce it by 100 % [11].

However, this work will make focus on the pH of the culture, another important factor affecting microalgae growth, as it determines the solubility and availability of CO₂ and essential nutrients and has a significant impact on algal metabolism [8]. Most microalgae tolerate wide pH intervals, but out of this range the yield is greatly reduced. This variable varies as a result of the reactions involved in the consumption of carbon and nitrogen species from the culture medium. It is usually controlled by injecting CO₂ as it also supports the supply of carbon to the culture medium [12]. The photosynthesis performed by microalgae changes the acidity of the culture medium, increasing the pH, while CO₂ injections reduce it [13].

Traditional operation usually controls pH by injecting CO₂ with an on/off controller. This is mostly due to the difficulty of developing a model that adequately reflects pH dynamics and is suitable for the development of control algorithms.

In the last years, several research lines have made a great effort to advance

in this regard. As a consequence, nowadays is easy to find mainly three kind of models. Dynamic models based on first principles consider fluid dynamics, mass transfer and biological phenomena that take place in the process. This makes them suitable for process optimization and development of simulators, but make control algorithms tuning very challenging [14, 15, 16, 17]. Secondly, linear models relating the measured pH to the CO₂ injection at the operation point facilitate the development of controllers [18, 19, 20, 21]. However, their simplicity leads to errors and need for frequent calibration, as pH dynamics change abruptly with weather and culture conditions. Lastly, with the emerging of artificial intelligence and machine learning, in the last few years several data-driven models have been developed. These are very useful for real-time fault detection and controller tuning, but require a large amount of data with a wide variety of conditions in order to adjust properly to the system [22, 23].

In terms of pH control, numerous techniques have been implemented in the recent years. Several Proportional-Integral-Derivative approaches have been proposed in the literature, given their enormous use and success in all kind of industries. An example of a PI controller with feedforward for solar radiation compensation can be found in [24]. More advanced applications of PID controllers such as event-based controllers can be found in [25] and [26]. Algorithms that have gained great attention in the last years such as predictive control approaches have also been implemented in raceway reactors for pH control purposes. Examples of this can be found in [22] and [27].

As a direct consequence of the challenges involved in modeling this system, adaptive control techniques are once again gaining in importance. These involve modifying the control law used by the controller to cope with the fact that the parameters of the system being controlled change drastically due to the variability in environmental conditions or in the system itself. The adaptive control process continuously and automatically measures the dynamic behavior of the system, compares it with the desired output and uses the difference to vary the adjustable system parameters or to generate an actuation signal so that optimal performance can be maintained regardless of changes in the system [28]. Some adaptive techniques applied to raceway reactors, implemented both with PI and predictive controllers, can be found in [23] and [29].

The aim of this work is to contribute in a new adaptive control solution for this problem with the implementation and evaluation of a hybrid structure of the Model Reference Adaptive Control (MRAC) for pH regu-

lation through CO₂ injection, combining the original scheme with a fixed proportional-integral (PI) controller. This hybrid control scheme contributes to improve the robustness and disturbance rejection capabilities of the classical MRAC control approach thanks to the combination with an inner PI loop. Notice that the adaptation law is now in charge of modifying the set-point of the inner loop instead of changing the control signal, as done in the classical MRAC implementation. The proposed algorithm was thoroughly analyzed using a first principles-based simulator that reflects the dynamics of a real raceway reactor and its performance was compared with a classical PI controller. Once it was proven to be a promising solution for the studied problem, the controller was implemented in the real raceway reactor in continuous mode (in June and July 2024). The results demonstrate how the proposed hybrid MRAC-PI control scheme properly adapts to the varying system dynamics the same closed-loop dynamics under different conditions.

This paper is structured as follows: section 2 describes the raceway reactor used in this work and the pH dynamics, while section 3 describes the control structure design. In section 4 a deep analysis using a first principles based simulator is made and results in the real facilities are shown. Finally, conclusions about the proposed controller and its performance are drawn in section 5.

2. Facilities and control problem statement

In this work an open reactor has been used, in particular the raceway reactor located at the IFAPA center, next to University of Almería (Almería, Spain), shown in Figure 1. It is composed by two 40 *m* long channels by a 1 *m* wide U-shaped bend, obtaining a total surface of 80 *m*². It has a depth of 30 *cm*, although it has been shown that the optimum height is around 15 *cm* [30]. In this work, results are presented both in the real facilities and in a first principles-based simulator that accurately describes the dynamics of this reactor [14].

This type of reactor is divided into three parts: (i) a paddlewheel to mix and impulse the culture along the channel, (ii) a 2 *m* depth sum where CO₂ and air injection is made to control pH and dissolved oxygen, respectively, and (iii) the channel through which microalgae circulate to capture solar radiation and perform photosynthesis [5].

The studied strain is *Scenedesmus*, suitable for the environmental conditions presented in Southern Spain. It is a fast-growing strain and can survive

Figure 1: Raceway reactor located at IFAPA center.

under a wide range of temperatures and pH conditions [31, 32]. Microalgae are grown in freshwater and nutrients are added to it during the dilution procedure.

The system is equipped with multiple sensors, recording all the variables involved in the process (pH, dissolved oxygen, temperature, level, etc.), included climatic variables (solar radiation, temperature, wind speed, among others), and operating conditions (dilution and harvesting rate, nutrient supply and others).

The pH is measured right after the sump (where CO_2 is injected) and at the end of the channel (before the paddlewheel). This last point is the target of the control algorithms, given that it is the most unfavorable and most challenging to control. This is due to the presence of a characteristic delay between the start of injection and its effect on pH, dictated by the distance between the sump and the sensor and the velocity at which the fluid flows through the channel. The paddle wheel speed is fixed so that culture flows at 0.2 m/s , resulting in a 5 min delay.

The pH is mainly influenced by CO_2 and solar radiation. When carbon dioxide is injected, after the delay time, the pH starts to decrease. When the injection is interrupted, the microalgae's photosynthetic activity causes the pH to rise again. It should be noted that the dynamic strongly depends

on environmental conditions, such as solar radiation and temperature, and on the culture conditions, such as biomass concentration or culture depth. These parameters will affect the photosynthetic activity and thus the pH variation.

This effect can be seen in Figure 2. It can be observed that, as mentioned previously, when CO₂ injection begins, after the characteristic delay time, pH starts decreasing. Once CO₂ injection is shut off, after the delay time has elapsed, the pH starts increasing again. It can also be noted that the dynamics change during the day, specially due to the variation on solar radiation. In the central hours of the day, as light in the medium is higher, the photosynthetic activity increases and the CO₂ injection to lower the pH is longer in time. On the other hand, during the first and last hours of the day, when solar radiation is low, as photosynthetic activity is low, the pH rise takes longer.

Figure 2: CO₂ injection and Photosynthetically Active PAR radiation (PAR) effect on pH

Therefore, the effect of CO₂ injection on pH can be modeled as a first-order system plus time delay:

$$\tau \cdot \frac{dpH(t)}{dt} + pH(t) = K_1 \cdot CO_2(t - t_d), \quad (1)$$

where $pH(t)$ is the measured pH at the end of the channel, $CO_2(t)$ is the CO₂ flow in L/min , t_d is the characteristic time delay, K_1 is the static gain

and τ is the time constant. Note that the delay time is constant and equal to 5 *min*, while K_1 and τ vary with the conditions, depending mostly on solar radiation, biomass concentration, medium temperature and level [23]. The oscillatory component that is overlapped with the first-order response is due to the recirculation of the culture along the channel and controlling it remains unimportant.

As the system dynamics change continuously, fixed-models do not work properly for controlling purposes, as they need to be constantly recalibrated. This issue encourages the use of adaptive techniques such as the MRAC algorithm, described in depth in the following section.

3. Model Reference Adaptive Control

When the parameters of the controlled process either are poorly known or vary during normal operation, the use of adaptive control techniques is usually required to obtain a high-performance control system. An adaptive system measures a certain index or performance using the inputs, the states, and the outputs of the system. From the comparison of the measured index and a set of given ones, the adaptation mechanism modifies the parameters of the adjustable system or generates an auxiliary input to maintain the index of performance close to the one specified [33].

In this way, in the MRAC, the desired performance is specified in terms of a reference model which gives the desired response to a command signal. The system has two feedback loops: an ordinary loop composed by the process and the controller, and a second loop that changes the controller parameters (θ) based on the error (e_m) between the measured output (y) and the output of the reference model (y_m) representing the desired closed-loop dynamics, as shown in Figure 3 [34, 35].

The MRAC system may be designed by three different strategies: MIT rule, Lyapunov rule, and theory of augmented error [35, 36]. In all three cases, the rule for updating the controller parameters (calculated by the adjustment mechanism in Figure 3) is of the form

$$\frac{d\theta(t)}{dt} = \gamma \cdot e_m(t) \cdot \phi(t), \quad (2)$$

Figure 3: Model Reference Adaptive Control scheme, adapted from [33]

where:

- γ is the adaptation gain. It aims to strike a balance between fast convergence and stability. A high adaptation gain can lead to quick parameter update and quicker convergence, but may also introduce instability and overshoot [37].
- e_m is the error, defined as the difference between the measured output of the system and the desired output, given by the reference model.
- ϕ is the negative gradient for the MIT rule and a regression vector in other cases, found by filtering inputs, outputs, and command signals [34, 35].

In this work, the MRAC is designed using Lyapunov's stability theory applied to systems with delay [38]. As shown in equation (1), the pH response to a CO₂ pulse can be modeled as a first-order system with delay around the operating point. Therefore, the system given by the equation (3) is considered to describe the process dynamics,

$$\frac{dy(t)}{dt} = -a_1 \cdot y(t) + a_2 \cdot u(t - t_d), \quad (3)$$

where $u(t)$ is the input to the process, $y(t)$ is the measured output, a_1 and a_2 are unknown parameters, and t_d is the delay time. The desired closed-loop response is given by equation (4),

$$\frac{dy_m(t)}{dt} = -a_{1,m} \cdot y_m(t) + a_{2,m} \cdot u_c(t - t_d), \quad (4)$$

where $u_c(t)$ is the command signal or setpoint, $y_m(t)$ is the model output, and $a_{1,m}$ and $a_{2,m}$ are the predetermined gains that establish the dynamics of the closed-loop system.

Let now introduce the adaptive control law to integrate the adaptation mechanism, described by equation (5).

$$u(t) = \theta_1(t) \cdot u_c(t - t_d) - \theta_2(t) \cdot y(t), \quad (5)$$

where $\theta_1(t)$ and $\theta_2(t)$ are the adaptation parameters.

As described before, the controller parameters are changed depending on the error between the measured and desired output, shown in equation (6)

$$e_m(t) = y(t) - y_m(t). \quad (6)$$

As the main objective of the controller is to minimize this error, it seems natural to formulate its differential equation as follows:

$$\frac{de_m(t)}{dt} = \frac{dy(t)}{dt} - \frac{dy_m(t)}{dt}, \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{de_m(t)}{dt} = & -a_1 \cdot y(t) + a_2 \cdot u(t - t_d) + \\ & a_{1,m} \cdot y_m(t) - a_{2,m} \cdot u_c(t - t_d). \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Then, let's add the term $a_{1,m} \cdot y(t) - a_{1,m} \cdot y_m(t)$ to it, resulting in the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{de_m(t)}{dt} = & -a_1 \cdot y(t) + a_2 \cdot u(t - t_d) + a_{1,m} \cdot y_m(t) \\ & - a_{2,m} \cdot u_c(t - t_d) + a_{1,m} \cdot y(t) - a_{1,m} \cdot y_m(t). \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Taking into account the expression (6) and reorganizing the terms, then the differential equation of the error results as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{de_m(t)}{dt} = & -a_{1,m} \cdot e_m(t) - (a_1 + a_2 \cdot \theta_2(t) - a_{1,m}) \cdot y(t) + \\ & (a_2 \cdot \theta_1(t) - a_{2,m}) \cdot u_c(t - t_d). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In equation (10), the error goes to zero if the adaptive parameters, θ_1 and θ_2 reach the following equilibrium values:

$$\bar{\theta}_1 = \frac{a_{2,m}}{a_2}, \quad \bar{\theta}_2 = \frac{a_{1,m} - a_1}{a_2}. \quad (11)$$

To create a mechanism that adjusts the parameters θ_1 and θ_2 to these values, let's introduce the following Lyapunov function, following the ideas presented in [34]:

$$V(e_m, \theta_1, \theta_2) = \frac{1}{2} \cdot [e_m^2(t) + \frac{1}{a_2 \cdot \gamma_1} \cdot (a_2 \cdot \theta_1(t) - a_{2,m})^2 + \frac{1}{a_2 \cdot \gamma_2} \cdot (a_1 + a_2 \cdot \theta_2(t) - a_{1,m})^2], \quad (12)$$

where γ_1 and γ_2 are the adaptation gains. The function is zero when the error is zero and the parameters θ_1 and θ_2 converge to the corresponding steady state values in equation (11). Then, the function is derived with respect to time, resulting as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV(t)}{dt} = & e_m(t) \cdot \frac{de_m(t)}{dt} + \frac{1}{\gamma_1} \cdot (a_2 \cdot \theta_1(t) - a_{2,m}) \cdot \frac{d\theta_1(t)}{dt} + \\ & \frac{1}{\gamma_2} \cdot (a_1 + a_2 \cdot \theta_2(t) - a_{1,m}) \cdot \frac{d\theta_2(t)}{dt}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

By substituting equation (10) into (13) it is obtained the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dV(t)}{dt} = & -a_{1,m} \cdot e_m^2(t) + \\ & \frac{1}{\gamma_1} \cdot (a_2 \cdot \theta_1(t) - a_{2,m}) \cdot \left(\frac{d\theta_1(t)}{dt} + \gamma_1 \cdot e_m(t) \cdot u_c(t - t_d) \right) + \\ & \frac{1}{\gamma_2} \cdot (a_1 + a_2 \cdot \theta_2(t) - a_{1,m}) \cdot \left(\frac{d\theta_2(t)}{dt} - \gamma_2 \cdot e_m(t) \cdot y(t) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

Therefore, if the adaptation parameters are updated as:

$$\frac{d\theta_1(t)}{dt} = -\gamma_1 \cdot e_m(t) \cdot u_c(t - t_d), \quad \frac{d\theta_2(t)}{dt} = \gamma_2 \cdot e_m(t) \cdot y(t), \quad (15)$$

equation (14) results in:

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = -a_{1,m} \cdot e_m^2(t). \quad (16)$$

Since it is negative semidefinite, it is Lyapunov stable. Moreover, by differentiating equation (16) with respect to time, the following expression is obtained:

$$\frac{d^2V(t)}{dt^2} = -2 \cdot a_{1,m} \cdot e_m(t) \cdot \frac{de_m(t)}{dt}. \quad (17)$$

If equation (10) is substituted in (17), it can be seen that $\frac{d^2V(t)}{dt^2}$ is a function of $e_m(t)$, $y(t)$ and $u_c(t - t_d)$, which are bounded signals. Therefore, $\frac{d^2V(t)}{dt^2}$ is bounded and $\frac{dV(t)}{dt}$ is continuous, so the system is Lyapunov stable and locally Lipschitz [34].

The MRAC ensures asymptotic output tracking, can handle disturbances and faults, has a clear physical explanation, and is simple to implement. Yet using only this controller comes with drawbacks like limited fault tolerance compared to hybrid approaches, as well as unreliable transient response or tracking performance [39].

To address this issue, in this work a PI controller is included to the MRAC control loop, resulting the scheme shown in Figure 4 [40]. The only difference with the original MRAC formulation is that now the process (equation (3)) is a PID-based feedback control loop. Therefore, the MRAC mechanism is in charge of adjusting the setpoint of the closed-loop system. The tuning procedure of the parameters (reference model, the PI controller and the adaptation gains) is explained in the following section.

Figure 4: Hybrid MRAC-PID scheme

4. Results

4.1. Controller tuning

In this work, a PI (proportional-integral) controller has been used for the closed-loop system shown in Figure 4. The model used for its tuning is a first-order with delay transfer function as shown in equation (18), that relates

the pH response with changes in the CO₂ injection flow [23]. This equation is the Laplace transformation of equation (1).

$$G(s) = \frac{pH(s)}{CO_2(s)} = \frac{K_1}{\tau s + 1} \cdot e^{-t_d s}. \quad (18)$$

For implementing the PI controller, the parallel structure was used, shown in equation (19), where K_p is the proportional gain and K_i the integral gain calculated as $K_i = K_p/T_i$, with T_i is the integral time constant:

$$C(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s}. \quad (19)$$

Its parameters were tuned using the SIMC rule for first-order systems with delay developed in [41], which states as follows:

$$K_p = \frac{1}{K_1} \frac{\tau + \frac{t_d}{3}}{\tau_{bc} + t_d}, \quad (20)$$

$$T_i = \min \left\{ \tau + \frac{t_d}{3}, 4(\tau_{bc} + t_d) \right\}, \quad (21)$$

where τ_{bc} is the closed-loop time constant and equals the delay time ($\tau_{bc} = t_d = 300$ s), following the recommendations given in [41]. The designed PI also includes the anti-windup structure with the tracking constant equal to the integral time ($T_t = T_i$) due to the actuators limits ($[0 - 12]$ L/min).

For tuning the inner loop PI controller, a first-order model with average parameters was used. The parameters' values of the model (shown in equation (22)) have been obtained as the average of almost 500 models obtained for different conditions in [23]. In this way, even if a perfectly fitting model is not used, it can be ensured that a representative model of the behavior of the system under a large combination of climatic and culture conditions is used:

$$G(s) = \frac{pH(s)}{CO_2(s)} = \frac{K_1}{\tau s + 1} \cdot e^{-t_d s} = \frac{-0.15}{1000s + 1} \cdot e^{-300s}. \quad (22)$$

Regarding the adaptation mechanism tuning, the reference model was designed taking into account the choice made previously for the closed-loop time constant. Therefore, its expression is shown in equation (23), where $\tau_{bc} = t_d = 300$ s and the closed-loop gain is unitary in order to achieve zero

steady-state error. It must be noted that the reference model relates the desired output performance to the imposed reference or command signal:

$$G_{ref} = \frac{pH(s)}{pH_{SP}(s)} = \frac{1}{300s + 1} \cdot e^{-300s}. \quad (23)$$

It must be also noted that the studied system presents a natural excitation. That is, it is not necessary to impose changes in the pH's setpoint in order to generate variation in its value and dynamics. This is thanks to permanent disturbances (such as solar radiation, that provokes photosynthetic activity and therefore an increase in pH) and the existing coupling between variables (such as dilution rate, which provokes an increase or decrease in pH, depending on the water composition). However, the common way to operate the real facilities is to wait until there is enough solar radiation for microalgae to produce photosynthesis and then start running the control algorithm. In this way, it is usual to begin CO₂ injections when pH reaches a value of 8.3 (or similar) and lower it to its operating point at 8. Therefore, this will be taken into account in both simulation and real facilities implementation.

With all this, and the development of the algorithm described in section 3, the hybrid MRAC - PI block diagram is shown in Figure 5. It can be easily distinguished the closed-loop system, consisting of the PI controller with anti-windup and the process, and the adaptation mechanism. It is also important to establish the "control flag", in charge of turning on and off the control algorithm. As commented previously, the control will start running when there is enough solar radiation and will be shut down when radiation falls below a certain value. During the night, when the control algorithm is not running, the adaptation parameters remain constant at their last value and the adapted reference created by the adaptation mechanism follows the measured pH.

For the adaptation gains, there is no rule in literature to determine their values. Thus, they are usually determined using systematic strategies such as trial and error, optimization algorithms or advanced control design methods [37, 42, 43]. Therefore, a comparative study was carried out for different values of the parameter.

Figure 5: Hybrid MRAC-PI block diagram

Figure 6: Comparative study of the effect of adaptation gain.

In Figure 6 it can be seen the behavior for the classical PI and three different MRAC's configuration. It can be noted that:

- Adaptation gains established as $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = 10^{-6}$ constitute a very conservative solution, obtaining a pH dynamic similar to the one obtained by the classical PI. This configuration obtains a slow reduction of the error between the system and the reference model outputs.
- Adaptation gains established as $\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 = 10^{-5}$ provide a very aggressive solution. pH's behavior contains wide overshooting and the control signal varies abruptly. In this case, the error decreases quickly but with very aggressive oscillations.
- Adaptation gains established as $\gamma_1 = 10^{-5}$ and $\gamma_2 = 10^{-6}$ obtain a perfect compromise between both previous solutions. It provides a quicker response than the classical PI but with a less aggressive behavior. The error is evolution faster than the first case but smoother than the second one.

In order to compare the performance of the controller in each case, the IAE (Integral Absolute Error), ISE (Integral Square Error), ITAE (Integral of Time multiplied Absolute Error), ITSE (Integral of Time multiplied Square Error) and CE (Control Effort) were calculated, following the expressions shown in equations (24) and (25):

$$IAE = \int_0^T |e(t)| dt, \quad ISE = \int_0^T e^2(t) dt, \quad ITAE = \int_0^T |e(t)| \cdot t dt, \quad (24)$$

$$ITSE = \int_0^T e^2(t) \cdot t dt, \quad CE = \int_0^T \Delta u(t) dt. \quad (25)$$

In Table 1 the performance indexes for each simulated strategy in Figure 6 are shown, weighted with respect to the classical PI scheme. It can be seen that the best compromise is obtained by the first configuration, obtaining the lowest indexes regarding the error and a control effort a little higher than the one obtained by the PI controller. Therefore, the resulting adaptation gains were $\gamma_1 = 1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ and $\gamma_2 = 1 \cdot 10^{-6}$.

	IAE	ISE	ITAE	ITSE	CE
PI	1	1	1	1	1
MRAC ₁ ($\gamma_1 = 10^{-5}$, $\gamma_2 = 10^{-6}$)	0.791	0.923	0.709	0.886	1.285
MRAC ₂ ($\gamma_1 = 10^{-5}$, $\gamma_2 = 10^{-5}$)	0.821	0.971	0.726	0.937	1.617
MRAC ₃ ($\gamma_1 = 10^{-6}$, $\gamma_2 = 10^{-6}$)	0.957	0.972	0.929	0.956	1.087

Table 1: Comparative study of the effect of adaptation gain - Performance indexes

4.2. Simulation analysis

Once all the parameters have been tuned, in this section, a simulation study is carried out to demonstrate the improvements of the proposed algorithm over the classical PI controller. For this purpose, both strategies have been implemented in simulation during three days with different weather and culture conditions.

In the first place, an on/off controller with hysteresis was implemented in simulation for the three selected days. The results are shown in Figure 7, where it can be seen that the studied days present very different radiation, temperature and biomass concentration curves. The following can be noted:

- Day 1 presents a much lower radiation and temperature profile and has no presence of clouds. This affects the pH dynamics as the CO₂ injections decrease its value faster and its rise is slower, compared to days 2 and 3. The biomass concentration is also lower than on days 2 and 3.
- Day 2 has a higher temperature and radiation, but its profile is typical of a cloudy day. Regarding biomass concentration, it is higher than on day 1 and presents two small decreases during the day, probably due to dilution.
- Day 3 presents the higher temperature and radiation profiles and has no presence of clouds. Its biomass concentration value is similar to day 2, but has a much bigger decrease during the day. Regarding pH dynamics, it can be seen that CO₂ injection to lower it from 8.4 to 8 last longer than the other two days, especially during the central hours of the day. On the other hand, pH rises considerably faster when CO₂ flow is shut off.

Next, for each day shown in Figure 7 a first-order model with delay was identified. The listed differences in both weather and culture conditions,

Figure 7: On/Off controller simulation for three days with different conditions

which lead to different pH dynamics, affected the time constant and the static gain as expected. The models relating pH with CO_2 flow for each day are shown in equation (26), where it is proved that the three days present different pH dynamics:

$$\begin{aligned}
 G_{day1}(s) &= \frac{pH(s)}{CO_2(s)} = \frac{-0.0792}{1192s + 1} \cdot e^{-300s}, \\
 G_{day2}(s) &= \frac{pH(s)}{CO_2(s)} = \frac{-0.1019}{1622s + 1} \cdot e^{-300s}, \\
 G_{day3}(s) &= \frac{pH(s)}{CO_2(s)} = \frac{-0.1289}{2250s + 1} \cdot e^{-300s}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

The model identified for day 2 has been used for tuning the PI controller using the SIMC method described in section 4.1. The resulting PI was used both on the classical PI algorithm and in the proposed hybrid MRAC. Finally, both controllers have been implemented in simulation for the three selected days, comparing their performance in each case.

The results are shown in Figure 8, where each column represents a different day. In the first row it can be observed the pH dynamic for both strategies, the adapted setpoint for the MRAC scheme and the pH setpoint. As mentioned in section 4.1, the control algorithms start running when pH reaches a value of 8.3 and the radiation is above a minimum value, estab-

lished at 50 W/m^2 , and is shut off when radiation decreases below this value. While the control is on, the setpoint is set at 8. The second row shows the CO_2 flow for the compared algorithms and the third one shows the evolution of the adaptation parameters in the proposed hybrid MRAC scheme.

Figure 8: Classical PI and hybrid MRAC implementation in simulation for three days with different conditions

In all three cases it can be seen that the hybrid MRAC strategy is more aggressive at the beginning of the day, obtaining a quicker response and leading pH to the setpoint in less time than the classical PI. After the central hours of the day, in days 1 and 3, the MRAC's control signal is lower than the PI's one, obtaining a better performance in the pH's behavior and maintaining it near the setpoint for longer. However, in the second day, both controllers behave almost the same after the pH has reached the setpoint, obtaining a similar evolution of the pH.

Regarding the adaptation parameters, it can be seen a similar evolution throughout the day for the three studied cases, but the second day presents more oscillations to make up for the cloudy profile of the solar radiation.

In Table 2 the performance indexes (IAE, ITAE, CE) are shown for both strategies, as well as the the ratio between both of them. It should be taken into account that the PI controller was tuned for the model obtained from the second day. Therefore it is expected to obtain a good PI performance and no big difference is awaited between MRAC and PI for this day. As

can be seen in Table 2, this is fulfilled: the PI has the lowest IAE and ITAE for day 2 and the ratio between MRAC and PI performance is higher than the other days. However, the proposed algorithm achieves a slightly better performance. Regarding days 1 and 3, the hybrid MRAC structure achieves an IAE almost 50 % smaller and it reduces the ITAE in an 80 %, demonstrating the adaptation capabilities of the proposed control algorithm. Lastly, the ratio between MRAC and PI control effort is almost the same for all three scenarios, presenting a higher control effort the studied algorithm.

		Hybrid MRAC + PI	Classical PI	MRAC/PI
IAE	Day 1	331	638.78	0.5181
	Day 2	492.31	589.59	0.835
	Day 3	381.15	753.45	0.5058
ITAE	Day 1	1.9295 e+06	6.9259 e+06	0.2786
	Day 2	3.3081 e+06	3.6066 e+06	0.9172
	Day 3	2.6866 e+06	9.3773 e+06	0.2865
CE	Day 1	25.223	20.981	1.2022
	Day 2	37.065	30.988	1.1961
	Day 3	27.259	23.261	1.1719

Table 2: Performance indexes of classical PI and hybrid MRAC for three days

The obtained results prove the need for this kind of adaptive controllers, due to their better performance and their ability to adapt to the variety of dynamics that the system may present. It can be concluded that the advantages this kind of strategies present when the model is accurate are not significant (although it slightly improves the performance), but is definitely necessary when the model is not faithful to the real dynamics.

4.3. Results in real facilities

After the adaptation parameters where tuned and the simulation study was carried out, the proposed scheme was implemented in the real facilities described in section 2.

The results are shown in Figures 9 and 10 for 12 days distributed in the months of June and July. In both cases it can be seen that control starts when PAR radiation is greater than $50 W/m^2$ and pH reaches a value of 8.3, and is shut off when radiation decreases under $50 W/m^2$. As explained in section 3, the pH setpoint is established at 8 and the adaptation loop is

in charge of changing the setpoint received by the closed loop. These two setpoints can be observed in the shown results.

Figure 9: Hybrid MRAC implementation in real facilities - June

Figure 10: Hybrid MRAC implementation in real facilities - July

In all twelve days, the proposed structure achieves a good performance and a great pH regulation, regardless of the varying conditions. In both

datasets there are sunny and cloudy days, but the adaptation parameters are able to deal with the changes this provokes in the pH dynamics. It should also be noted that the temperature profile is wider in June, existing a bigger difference between its minimum and maximum value, and CO₂ flow is greater in the results shown in Figure 9. Regarding the adaptation parameters, it can be seen that they both present a shape similar to the solar radiation, and present more oscillations when there are passing clouds. It should be taken into account that pH is coupled with more variables than the shown in the results, such as dissolved oxygen, biomass concentrations and dilution rate. However, all these aspects are not shown to avoid complicating the results' comprehension. The obtained results prove that adaptive control techniques are an adequate option for controlling this type of systems.

Figure 11: Results of implementation in two days of June and July

In Figure 11, two days of implementation of the proposed scheme can be seen. Figure 11a corresponds to the 23rd of June, while Figure 11b corresponds to the 15th of July. It can be noted that PAR radiation in Figure 11a is typical of a cloudy day, while in Figure 11b is the one of a sunny and clear day. Regarding temperature, its profile is similar in both days, presenting a slightly higher value in July results. In both cases, the hybrid MRAC is able to take the pH to the desired setpoint and maintain it during the whole operation of the controller. However, it can be seen that in the cloudy day,

the pH's behavior presents more oscillations than in the sunny day, where its shape is smoother. It can also be noted that the setpoint tracking is faster in the results obtained in July the 15th. As for the adaptation parameters, their variations are similar for both days, with more abrupt changes during the cloudy day, given that the adaptation mechanism has to cope with the changes the clouds provoke in the system's dynamic.

5. Conclusions and discussions

In this work, a hybrid model reference adaptive control (MRAC) was proposed for pH control in raceway reactor for microalgae production. The suggested algorithm was implemented in simulation and in the real facilities. The results demonstrate the effectiveness and advantages of the MRAC approach compared to the classical PI controller.

The proposed algorithm presents adaptability to variable conditions. The implementation of the MRAC hybrid controller in the real installations allowed observing its ability to adapt to changing conditions, such as solar radiation and temperature. Therefore, this can be presented as a solution for the modeling challenge presented in section 1. This algorithm is able to obtain a good regulation performance without the need of an accurate model that describes the relationship between pH and CO₂. On the contrary, it can be tuned with a simple first-order model.

The study has shown that adaptive controllers, such as hybrid-MRAC, offer a viable and efficient solution for managing dynamic systems under varying conditions. This is particularly relevant in microalgae production, where every factor can change drastically throughout the day and variables are deeply coupled among them. The MRAC's ability to adjust its parameters in real time allows it to maintain optimal pH control, which is crucial for maximizing the productivity and efficiency of bioreactors.

In summary, this study highlights the importance of adaptive controllers in the improvement of complex industrial processes and their potential to contribute to the sustainability and efficiency of microalgae production.

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